

THE DIDACTIC TRANSPOSITION IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION THROUGH INTERACTIVE METHODOLOGICAL WORKSHOPS AND THE BLOG

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ABSTRACT

This work, which describes an experience report, presents the theme of the application of didactic transposition in inclusive education through interactive methodological workshops and the blog. Its scientific relevance is presented in the condition of reporting to the academic public how teaching and learning methodologies can be developed using information and communication technologies and their various tools. Its social relevance is shown in the condition that it has the opportunity to give positive feedback to the wishes of the families of students with needs about the conditions of didactic-pedagogical engagement. The objective of this text is to publicize the work carried out at the State School of Elementary and High School “Padre Manoel da Nóbrega” - Vinhático, municipality of Montanha - ES. Starting from a deep reflection on my praxis, I realized that I would need to re-signify my practice and for that I would need to consider the principles of didactic transposition. This is how my pedagogical practice at the AEE took on a greater tendency towards the good, as the application of didactic transposition would become evident in it. The conclusion that can be reached is that the results with special students are relevant and successful, mediated by pedagogical practices carried out through interactive methodological workshops and with the support of the Blog.

Keywords: Students with special needs; Didactic transposition; Interactive methodological workshops; blog.

INTRODUCTION

The present report highlights the need to work with Specialized Educational Assistance (AEE) students with Intellectual Disabilities (ID) with methodologies that didactics, through empirical studies, have already proven are necessary for the promotion of learning. of any individual.

When considering the four pillars of Education, to highlight *learning to learn, learning to do, learning to live together and learning to be* (DELORS et al, 1996) as a condition for teaching and learning, especially the teaching of inclusive education, one cannot lose sight of them as an essential matter for didactic-pedagogical work, because, more than ever, it is necessary to work with active methodologies that respond to the wishes of students and society in relation to the work carried out in the classroom, considering that in addition to encouraging them, keeping them focused, it is also necessary that they promote learning in a way that allows the full development of their skills, such as reading, writing and calculate, these are so necessary for social experience.

So, in view of this need, I thought of applying it to the teaching of AEE, for 3 (three) students, from the after-hours service, 2 (two) from the 2nd EM, one (1) from the 7th M01 - in 2020 and, for the academic year of 2021, 3 (three) students, 1 (one), 3rd V01, 1(one) in the 1st V01 and 1(one) in the 8th M01, the principles of didactic transposition in the teaching of Portuguese Language-Literature. These were developed through interactive reading and text production workshops, interactive projects and the blog as active methodologies.

These methodologies began to be applied and linked to the creation of the *blog* in October 2019, coming to be consolidated as a didactic-pedagogical praxis during the year 2020 to August 2021, acting as a communication channel between the school and the students. who had access to the Internet, due to the need for social isolation, required as a safety health procedure because of the COVID-19 pandemic.

In August 2021, the return to face-to-face classes was mandatory and that's when I could see how much these practices made a difference in the school lives of these AEE students. Therefore, the results listed here will refer to the work of the academic years from 2020 to 2021, during the period of non-attendance classes. I thought of active methodologies, such as workshops, practical classes and interactive projects for reading and text production and the blog so that students could become the center of learning.

I worked with them on the programmed contents through methodological workshops based on the interactive model of reading, as it allowed my student to establish a meaningful dialogue between the text and the reader when, through the practice of reading, it triggers the prior knowledge that has and allows the reader to be situated and interested in the subject, and interest is the key to learning.

In this way, my practice broke with the routine, *open the book on that page, read the text, solve the questions, then the grammatical activities will be solved*, with the ascending and descending models of reading, allowing, therefore, that my student make a deeper and more

meaningful reading of the text, thus freeing themselves from the alienating effects of the school's content practices. This happened because the student participates, thinking, throughout the process, that is, it is not the practice of a mechanical, decoding and linear reading.

In this regard, Ribon Silva (2020, p. 67) makes the following statement: “the practice of reading is the key that frees the people of a country from the invisible shackles of alienation and ignorance caused by the school itself and the media of mass.” Therefore, it is up to the school to rethink its practices and offer all its students, with or without disabilities, the opportunity to acquire an integral and more humane education.

That said, due to the need to contribute to the provision of quality training for DI students of the AEE, the following objectives were listed:

- ✓ Encourage the active participation of students in the teaching-learning process, through workshops and projects of reading and production of texts with different themes, friendship, love, family, health, environment, linked in books, newspapers, blogs, videos, films , recipe sites etc. in order to facilitate intradisciplinary and interdisciplinary approaches and transversality, through the recreation and creation of texts.
- ✓ Use the *blog* as an active methodology, a technological instrument to give visibility, value and archive, as in a portfolio, the results of research, the production of texts and videos produced by students, which can be accessed and appreciated by the family and society in general.

DEVELOPMENT

As Plato (428-348 BC) already argued when comparing the knowledge that there is nothing good or bad, but two things: wisdom which is good and ignorance which is evil. And, given this statement, a question arises: *To what extent do school practices contribute to good or bad in the AEE teaching modality?* The analysis of methodological practices allowed me to enumerate the following statements: if my student, during my classes, sat reading fragments of literary texts, tasteless, devoid of meaning and ability to arouse their interest and will, I would only I could say that the methodological practices carried out in this way do not contribute significantly to the student becoming enlightened, tending more towards the bad than towards the good.

Starting from a deep reflection on my praxis, I realized that I would need to re-signify my practice and for that I would need to consider the principles of didactic transposition. This is how my pedagogical practice at the AEE took on a greater tendency towards the good, as it would show the application of didactic transposition.

For this, I considered the theory listed by Souza (2021) that,

Make it clear that Didactic transposition is the ability to make oneself understood and understood in the linguistic field of the other; in the epistemological field of the other, in the semantic field of the other, that is, an engineer needs to make the master builders and other agents understand what he explained in his architectural project. For this, it is necessary to adjust the vocabulary terms with which the idea is intended to be expressed; otherwise, there will be no communication, considering that there will be no understanding of his thinking or his technical work proposal (SOUZA, 2021, p. 56).

As well as taking advantage of the multiplicity of TCT's, in work proposals that address one or more components in an intradisciplinary, interdisciplinary or transdisciplinary and transversal way with different themes such as environment, science and technology, food safety, economy, health, among others. . This reminded me of another author, Lisboa et al, when he makes the following consideration:

Lesson, intervention, and support plans should be at the level of advancement and student interest. All this, to motivate and challenge them and not the other way around, as has happened. For, if the teacher does not seduce and enchant them with his teachings, he can become a serious candidate to lose the battle to his students and their charming toys (LISBOA et al, 2020, sp).

These toys are called cell phones and electronic games, which keep our students passive and inert while they play. So, I thought if you can't beat them, join them, and I brought to the classroom a technological instrument in which you could find educational games, informative texts, videos with different subjects, which was the *blog* . The advantage of the *blog* is that the student will not only be a passive spectator or a compulsive player who only consumes the information linked there, because the creation of a *blog page* , in which they had free access and could act and interact throughout the process of preparing poetic texts, informative, among others, videos to be published. Thus, they become knowledge-producing agents in an increasingly technological world.

Here I remembered that when I wrote a text, the teacher corrected it and it was kept filed in the notebook. Therefore, the only reader was the teacher who aimed to correct and obtain an objective value to the student's work, the grade. In this sense, Geraldi (2001, p. 31) asks the

following question: “What is the fun in writing a text that will not be read by anyone or that will be read only by one person (who, by the way, will correct the text and grade it?)?”

I always saw that it made no sense; my texts did not fulfill their functions, which was to take my ideas and opinions to other people, besides the teacher; however, they were seen only as a school activity. Here I thought of using the *blog* as an active methodology to re-signify this praxis, a vehicle of communication between my student and possible readers who, in addition to producing the texts, were corrected by me, rewritten by the student to be published on the blog, fulfilling, thus its social function, which is to establish communication between the writer and the reader.

The blog was thought because it allowed, in addition to giving visibility to my practice, it would serve to archive the work done by my student in the form of an electronic portfolio, with infinite possibility of archiving.

To exemplify all this theory, I will make a cutout, in which the activities developed throughout this period will be presented, since it is about productions and records of 3 students from AEE - DI, from after school, in the years 2020 and 2021.

Here I will describe the activities developed with the student LOSA of the student - from the 7th M01 and who attends the AEE, in the afternoon.

On the 11/02/2020th, during two hours of classes, I worked with the technique, the *Mysterious Box*. My objective with this class was to stimulate motor, visual, auditory, tactile, gustatory perception and balance, as well as cognitive and linguistic skills for writing texts. During its realization, the student (DI) remained attentive and concentrated, writing his text and, according to the teachers of the common room, this attitude is not perceived in the classroom, because he is usually agitated and does not comply with his activities, as it should. As he had *guessed*, what was in the box, I gave him chocolates as a prize. Following the class, he watched videos on how to make chocolate, took notes, chocolate cake recipe videos.

Along the same lines and, to maintain the concentration of the LOSA student, on - 18/02/2020, for 3h/a, the film *The Fantastic Chocolate Factory* was shown. He remained focused and attentive the entire time. So, after the appraisal, I had an informal conversation with him about the themes and values addressed in the plot. Then I asked him to write a summary of the film. Through a few key questions, he recalled each character's behavior and took notes. In the end, the summary was pretty consistent with the movie. Here, due to the fact that he opened the magic box, due to my absence, seeing what was inside, I received the prize (candy) unfairly, the values were discussed; for that, I asked him if he would keep the chocolate factory, he said yes, I replied, saying no, because he had been dishonest, when opening the

magic box, in the previous class, during my absence. So, I explained to him the importance of being honest, being cordial among other values, taking the attitudes and behaviors of the characters in the film as examples.

On 03/10/2020 - 3h / a - I started the practical classes, the objective of reading and interpreting descriptive and instructive texts and executing the instructions received, which was to make brigadiers. In this case, here I took into account the pillars of learning to do education. With this student, a price survey was carried out at the supermarket, the ingredients of the brigadeiro, this was the last task, as classes were suspended, because of the pandemic.

- ✓ Activities developed with students – A. dos SA and MEDGP, from the 2nd V01-EM, in the 2020 academic year.

As mentioned before, texts need to be worked on in a way that makes sense to the student; So, on 02/12/2020 - 3h/a, I worked with the book *A Invasão das Borboletas*, the objectives of the class, conceptualizing, reading, interpreting, creating and recreating narrative text, the tale. In this case, after reading the story. I asked the following questions what happened? With whom? When? Where? The climax. How did it end? Then, I performed a video showing about the metamorphosis of butterflies, the making of butterflies with peanuts, tissue paper and white glue and, finally, a conversation about the importance of preserving the environment.

Taking as a starting point the need to apply the pillars of education, learning to do, on - 03/03/2020 - 3h/a - The objective of the class: To produce narrative text focusing on the first person singular (I) to from a practical class, which was the manufacture of a caramelized banana candy, because the concrete experience serves as a basis for abstraction, that is, the elaboration of a text in the first person d singular, reporting how they felt after doing the sweet.

Here it is worth remembering that, in addition to the Portuguese language, my student also worked with interdisciplinarity in Mathematics, when he measured and weighed the ingredients, to make the sweet, in Science, the issue of hygiene when handling food, transversality, through food safety with the use of fresh ingredients and common sense when eating sweets.

In March 2020, face-to-face classes were suspended because of the pandemic. Students started to receive *Non-Presential Pedagogical Activities* (APNP's) that were also published on the blog. From these dates, the service became collaborative.

The 2021 school year also started with remote activities, with the delivery of printed APNP's, the use of Google Classroom and, therefore, the AEE continued in the collaborative until August. With the return of face-to-face classes, the AEE service, in the counter shift, also returned and, thus, activities were resumed.

For the year 2021, I will highlight some activities developed both with the student LOSA, from the 8th M01, and with the student JPPG, student of the 1st V02.

With the return of face-to-face classes, I was able to work with a variety of themes, subjects with more dynamics, because, due to the fact that there were computers and access to the Internet network, I was able to offer, in addition to texts and written interpretations, I was able to work through the QUIZ . Apply the notions of addition and subtraction in *online math games* . Develop precision in the use of technological resources (typing, research and solving mathematical games), among others.

But here, I will highlight the reading and production workshops developed from September to December 2021 with LOSA students, from the 8th M01 and the student JPP G – 1st V01, because that was when I was able to work the Portuguese language with transversality in *Citizenship and Civics* and *Science and Technology* , through the interpretation of the literary text in the form of a cartoon, each one in its specific days. It all started with the screening of the movie *The Little Prince* , because in this case, I was able to bring to the center of our informal conversations the importance of family and the importance of friendship in people's lives, as well as other values, such as resilience, patience and others more.

The most interesting thing was realizing that even though it was the same activity for both of them, each wrote their summary in their own way. LO, for example, narrated the facts in a longer text, while the student JP reported the essence of the film, through the text that talks about the importance of friendship and love in the family. Most importantly, I could see how focused, attentive and interested they remained throughout the process. The texts of the two students are published and archived on the blog.

In the meantime, I also worked with the MEDGP student, from the 3rd V01 in 2021. I will emphasize some of the workshops that were developed from September to December 2021, which, in my view, were significant for this student's learning.

On 09/08/2021, I worked with a Portuguese Language discipline as a transversality in *the Environment, Citizenship and Civics* . The main objective was to elaborate a dissertation-argumentative text. Theme: *Recycling solid waste is fundamental for the preservation of the environment* . In this case, I asked the student some questions about what we normally do with garbage. She was emphatic, we threw it away. It was then that I threw on the table several toys,

old invitations, game pieces, that is, solid waste, which would be discarded in nature. That's when I started questioning the dangers that this garbage posed to life on the planet. She wrote the text, as it was proposed, from there, she read more about the importance of recycling. And, to show how beautiful nature is, she was invited to take pictures of the plants in the schoolyard. In this case, in addition to the transversal approach in the Environment, there was also the practice of interdisciplinarity in Art and Science and Technology, using the cell phone to take pictures. Both the text and the photos were published on the blog.

I could not fail to mention that the student in question is very agitated, flustered and, therefore, there are days when she cannot even concentrate to carry out the proposed activities, and it is on these days that I invite her to relax and listen to music. orchestrated by musicians like Richard Cleyderman. Every time, I notice that the agitation subsides and she starts to solve the proposed activities.

Here I will return to the student JPPG 1stV02, because there is an activity that was developed, which deserves to be reported. On 08/17/21, I helped him in the interdisciplinary activities of the Language Area. Objective: Record a video talking about why the student likes the city where he lives. The result was surprising; from the text, prepared with my help, the student prepared a video, edited it and published it on the You Tube website. I was surprised by the result, because the student is shameful, his voice is not even heard in the classroom, according to the teachers, and suddenly he lets out his voice and imposes himself through the video and discovers that his dream is to improve his practice as a video editor. Thus, in addition to having his work published on YouTube, he was also published on the blog.

Among all the activities developed, one of them also deserves our attention, which was the Project *Poetizando e Proseando na Escola*, developed between the months of October, November and December in partnership with another AEE teacher, GC, whose main objective was to give visibility to AEE students and show other professionals and students that AEE students also have skills and talents that need to be worked on and developed by and at school.

Thus, it is also important to point out that, from the workshops, which are generally thematic, I worked with all the disciplines and, the macro-areas of the Contemporary Transversal Themes, through informal conversations, guide them on different topics, such as citizenship, the environment, the proper use of social networks, as well as I was able to make interdisciplinary approaches to the contents of the curriculum.

It is worth remembering that, in order to carry out the activities, the students remained focused and, thinking about what they were doing, and it is there in this process that they make use of previous general knowledge, as well as their talents, creativity and feelings to solve the

questions that are presented and it is there that I could perceive the worldview they have, the values they believe in, family life, fears, dreams, concerns about the future, talents, the level of linguistic and mathematical knowledge, In short, it is there that the affective bond, so necessary in the teaching-learning process, was established between me and them.

All activities are published and archived on the blog and today it has more than 8,800 views and 65 comments and this allowed me to have positive *feedback* on the activities I was developing with these students.

The most interesting thing is that these methodologies can be replicated, workshops, projects, registration and publication on the blog. However, it is worth remembering that, due to the volume of materials produced, texts, photos, research results, keeping the blog updated is a great challenge, but little by little, among the possibilities, all tasks are published, so that fulfill their social function.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The teacher, as responsible for the teaching-learning process, whether for common room students or for AEE students, needs to improve his practice more and more, through active methodologies that contemplate the principles of didactic transposition in order to promote the teaching equity.

In addition, he cannot lose sight of the fact that students with Intellectual Disabilities are capable of learning, provided that dynamic, challenging activities are offered, in line with their level of prior knowledge and that manage to arouse their interest and actively involve them. throughout the teaching-learning process.

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